

Speciation studies of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of L-glutamic acid in urea-water mixtures

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Abstract : The speciation of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of L-glutamic acid has been investigated pH-metrically in urea-water mixtures (0–36.83%, w/v) at 303 K and an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³. The predominant species detected for Pb^{II} is ML; for Hg^{II} ML and MLH; for Cd^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} ML, ML₂ and ML₂H₂; for Ni^{II} ML, ML₂, ML₂H and for Cu^{II} ML, ML₂, ML₂H and ML₂H₂. The trend in the variation of stability constants of the complexes with the dielectric constant of the medium is attributed to the electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces and complexing ability of urea.

Keywords : Speciation studies, glutamic acid, urea-water mixtures.

L-Glutamic acid (Glu) acts as a neurotransmitter¹ and as a precursor of γ -aminobutyric acid². Because of its capacity to induce depolarising effects, it acts as an excitatory transmitter³ in cerebral cortex. In many animals Glu is the most abundant intra-cellular amino acid. The interaction of the carboxylate side chain of Glu with the metal ions is of importance in metalloenzymes and in metal-catalysed reactions. Hence, a biomimetic study was undertaken for Glu complexes of some toxic and essential metal ions, viz. Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}. Urea-water mixtures were chosen as medium since urea acts as a denaturant of biological macromolecules. The presence of urea in aqueous solution considerably increases the dielectric constant of the medium and these solutions are expected to mimic the physiological conditions where the concept of the equivalent solution dielectric constant⁴ for protein cavities is applicable. The present study is useful to understand (i) the role played by the active site cavities in biological molecules, (ii) the type of complex formed by the metal ion and (iii) the bonding behaviour of the protein residues with

the metal ion. The types of complexes formed and their relative concentrations under the present experimental conditions represent the possible forms of metal ions in the biological fluids and speciation represents the biological activity of these metals in the presence of glutamic acid.

Results and discussion

Alkalimetric titration curves in urea-water mixtures reveal that the acido-basic equilibria of Glu is active in the pH-range 1.5–10.0. Based on the active forms of the ligand in this pH-range, models containing various numbers and combination of complex species are generated using an expert system package CEES⁵. These models are inputted to the computer program, MINQUAD75⁶ along with the alkalimetric titration data. The best fit model is selected using the statistical parameters of the least square residuals. The final values of the formation constants of the complexes are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Best fit chemical models of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}-glutamic acid complexes in urea-water mixtures

Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

% w/v urea	log β_{mlh} (SD)					
	Pb		Cd		Hg	
	110	110	120	122	110	111
00.00	4.35 (17)	3.99 (12)	7.22 (10)	22.38 (50)	10.96 (4)	13.41 (5)
05.80	5.23 (99)	3.92 (36)	7.27 (33)	23.14 (46)	9.95 (15)	12.79 (26)
20.31	9.19 (89)	–	7.38 (26)	24.14 (27)	11.37 (55)	15.14 (93)
29.64	10.58 (20)	4.18 (63)	7.57 (81)	22.53 (30)	11.94 (9)	14.90 (21)
36.83	10.65 (12)	4.58 (46)	7.77 (47)	22.43 (54)	13.22 (13)	14.53 (67)

Solute-solvent interactions :

Born's classical treatment⁷ accounts to a plot of formation constants, $\log \beta$ versus $1/D$ (D is the dielectric constant of the medium) should be linear. The changes in $\log \beta$ values of Glu complexes of Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with $1/D$ are non-linear. Maximum stability of complexes was observed at 20.31% of urea with a dielectric constant of 86.04. At the higher percentage of urea, again there was a slight increase. Dielectric constant and long range interactions are not responsible for the stability trend. The cation stabilizing nature of co-solvents, specific urea-water interactions, charge dispersion and specific interactions of urea with solute indicated by the changes in the solubility of different species in aquo-organic mixtures account for the deviation from classical linear relationship of $\log \beta$ with $1/D$. Different types of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces dominate in different ranges of concentration of urea-water mixtures. The cumulative effect of both electrostatic and non-electrostatic interactions causes the non-linearity of stability constants of different species.

Distribution diagrams :

The different forms of Glu are LH_3^+ , LH_2 , LH^- and L^{2-} in the pH-regions of 1.5–3.5, 2.0–5.5, 5.0–9.5 and 8.5–11.0, respectively. The present study is confined to narrow pH ranges for different metals as given in Tables 1 and 2.

Distribution diagrams (Figs. 1 and 2) were drawn using

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams of glutamic acid complexes of (A) Pb^{II} , (B) Cd^{II} , (C) Hg^{II} in 20.31% of urea medium.

Fig. 2. Species distribution diagrams of glutamic acid complexes of (A) Co^{II} , (B) Ni^{II} , (C) Cu^{II} and (D) Zn^{II} in 20.31% of urea medium.

the formation constants (Tables 1 and 2) of the best fit models. The patterns of the distribution of species with pH show that the concentration of species are affected by urea. This trend depends on the relative solvation of urea. The formation equilibria, based on the above observations, are represented below. The charges of the species are omitted for clarity.

Experimental

Solutions of Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} nitrates and Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} chlorides have been prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple-distilled water. An aqueous solution of L-glutamic acid (E. Merck, Germany) is also prepared. To increase the solubility of the Glu and to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts, mineral acid concentration in the above solutions has been maintained at 0.05 mol dm^{-3} . Urea of 99.5% purity (E. Merck) has been used without further purification. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the

data have been subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA). The strength of alkali has been determined using the Gran plot⁸ method.

Table 2. Best fit chemical models of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}-glutamic acid complexes in urea-water mixtures

Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

% w/v	log β _{mth} (SD)			
	110	120	121	122
urea				
		Co-glutamic acid		
00.00	4.58(14)	7.75(14)	–	22.94(34)
05.80	4.35(41)	6.80(45)	–	23.12(61)
11.52	4.22(8)	6.96(60)	–	23.29(68)
20.31	10.55(8)	13.88(24)	–	28.41(85)
29.64	10.15(42)	13.27(33)	–	27.82(67)
36.83	9.92(38)	13.55(35)	–	27.07(9)
		Ni-glutamic acid		
00.00	5.14(70)	9.56(50)	16.47(20)	–
05.80	3.70(35)	6.75(15)	14.93(51)	–
11.52	4.72(14)	8.44(55)	15.23(59)	–
20.31	10.06(63)	15.80(47)	24.34(43)	–
29.64	9.99(25)	14.66(68)	22.63(65)	–
36.83	9.88(13)	14.63(46)	21.69(26)	–
		Cu-glutamic acid		
00.00	7.99(11)	14.49(5)	19.50(19)	24.11(7)
05.80	5.39(65)	8.41(39)	17.09(53)	21.86(75)
11.52	5.46(52)	9.59(5)	17.84(5)	22.43(5)
20.31	9.34(45)	14.10(10)	22.91(8)	29.39(16)
29.64	–	16.76(31)	24.71(23)	28.41(36)
36.83	–	19.82(8)	24.09(9)	27.43(5)
		Zn-glutamic acid		
00.00	4.90(5)	8.88(5)	–	22.94(5)
05.80	4.21(73)	6.67(99)	–	23.41(98)
11.52	4.63(36)	8.45(41)	–	22.25(69)
20.31	7.97(55)	12.16(79)	–	–
29.64	7.12(38)	10.40(75)	–	–
36.83	6.97(59)	10.34(71)	–	23.30(77)

The titrations have been carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of urea maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with sodium nitrate at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. An ELICO (Model LI-120) pH-meter (readability 0.01) has been used to monitor the changes in H⁺ concentration. The glass electrode has been equilibrated in a well stirred urea-water mixture containing inert electrolyte. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbondioxide on the response of glass electrode are accounted for in the form of correction factor⁹.

Titrations of strong acid with alkali have been carried

out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibrium was achieved. The calomel electrode has been refilled with urea-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of 1–3 mmol of mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm³. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.5, 1 : 5) of metal-ligand have been carried out with 0.4 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere¹⁰.

Conclusions :

On the basis of this study the following conclusions have been drawn :

(i) The biomimetic studies of metal ion complexes with L-glutamic acid indicate that all the complexes are protonated under acidic pH.

(ii) The non-linear relationship between log β values of species and 1/D of the solvent indicate that non-electrostatic interactions dominated the electrostatic forces.

(iii) Urea acts as denaturant and structure breaker of water and increases the dielectric constant of the medium. It also competes with the ligand for complexation with the metals.

(iv) At 1 : 3.5 metal-ligand ratio, the percentage of species are higher and complex formation is effective.

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